

EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT AND PROCESSING ON ISOTHERMAL CREEP PROPERTIES OF DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Commercially pure aluminium composites have been prepared containing Al₂O₃ particulates, Saffil or Carbon short fibres, and SiC whiskers with various volume fractions, using powder-blending. Isothermal creep tests have been performed and damage has been characterised using microscopy. The effect of processing has been investigated by comparing short fibre composites produced by powder-blending and infiltration followed in each case by extrusion. It was found that reinforcement distribution and shape were critical in determining creep resistance. Damage initiation was found to dominate composite behaviour, rather than load transfer considerations, for the short fibres and particulates. However, for the finer SiC whisker reinforcement, very good creep properties were observed.

KEYWORDS: damage, creep, cavitation, MMC, failure, reinforcement shape

INTRODUCTION

Previous work [1-3] has suggested that the load transfer effect in discontinuously reinforced composites can result in enhanced creep performance. When a stress is applied to a composite, some portion of the load is transferred to the reinforcement, as a consequence of its higher elastic modulus. As subsequent global plastic flow occurs in the matrix, this introduces a plastic misfit between the two phases, which further increases the load transfer to the reinforcement. This reduces the average stresses in the matrix, and hence reduces the driving force for creep. However, it is not necessarily true that load transfer will be the dominant effect on the composite creep behaviour. A high degree of load transfer also results in a high driving force for stress relaxation, and if this stress relaxation occurs in the form of microstructural damage, the mechanical properties of the composite can be degraded. While considerable work has been done on the creep behaviour of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites [1-3] some important questions have not previously been addressed.

It has been established that the fine oxide dispersion present in the matrix of powder-route composites leads to material with good creep resistance [2]. However, there has been little in the way of systematic comparisons to identify the relative importance of reinforcement and oxide dispersion in such systems.

Another important issue is that of damage stability. When damage is initiated in a composite, this will degrade the material by reducing the stiffness. However, if the damage is stable, and acts to reduce local stress concentrations, this may postpone failure, although the creep rate increases. Conversely, if the damage is unstable, this will lead rapidly to failure. It is therefore important to establish how the damage processes influence the overall mechanical response of the composite.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material Production

Discontinuously reinforced Al composites were prepared using powder blending or squeeze infiltration followed by extrusion [4]. The matrix used was commercially pure (CP) aluminium. The reinforcements used in the powder-route material were spherical and angular alumina particulates (with mean diameter 11 and 13 μm respectively, 20% volume fraction), chopped Saffil alumina fibres and chopped Carbon fibres, both with an average aspect ratio (in the final composite) of 5 and 3 μm diameter (volume fractions of 10 and 20%), and SiC whiskers with aspect ratio 5 and diameter 1 μm (volume fraction 10%). Composite was also prepared using squeeze infiltration followed by extrusion, with volume fractions of 10 and 20%, using Saffil alumina preforms. After extrusion, the average aspect ratio of the Saffil fibres was also 5. In addition, unreinforced CP Al was also prepared using powder blending and squeeze casting followed by extrusion. In the powder-route materials, there was a significant amount of oxide in the matrix, in the form of fine platelets ($\sim 100 \times 30 \text{ nm}$, 0.8 vol%) as demonstrated by Fig. 1. This was derived from the film present on the aluminium powder prior to fabrication, which was broken up and aligned during extrusion. Such a fine oxide dispersion acts as an efficient barrier to dislocation motion, so the powder-route matrices are themselves creep resistant.

Figure 1: SEM micrographs showing longitudinal sections of CP Al 10 vol% Saffil produced by (a) powder processing and (b) infiltration followed by extrusion.

Creep Testing

Isothermal creep tests were performed at 270 and 300°C with various loads, using a rig which incorporated a twin elliptical infra-red furnace, the load train being placed at the focal line of the furnace. This allowed visual direct access to the specimen during deformation. Both the axial and transverse strains of the specimen were monitored simultaneously during creep using scanning laser extensometry.

Microstructural Characterisation

In order to reveal the damage, specimens were carefully sectioned and electropolished. Details of the preparation procedure are given elsewhere[4]. Microstructural observations revealed that the powder-route composites contained a significant amount of fine oxide in the matrix, which was not present in the infiltrated composites. The grain structure was investigated by anodising the specimens[4]. In all cases the grain structure was elongated in the extrusion direction. Results of initial grain sizes and aspect ratios for selected composites are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Average grain sizes in as-fabricated composite, with unreinforced material, measured from anodised specimens, processed by powder-route (P) or Infiltration (I)

Material	Average Grain Length (µm)	σ_{n-1} (µm)	Average d (µm)	σ_{n-1} (µm)	Average Grain Aspect Ratio
20% Al ₂ O ₃ ang (P)	22	4	6	1	4
20% Al ₂ O ₃ sph (P)	21	3	5	1	5
20% Saffil (P)	12	3	4	1	3
20% Saffil (I)	32	6	23	6	2
10% SiC _w	60	8	2	1	30
20% C (P)	13	3	4	1	3
CP Al (P)	75	6	7	1	11

RESULTS

The composites did not exhibit significant secondary creep regimes; as has been reported previously with similar composites[5,6]. This is demonstrated by Fig. 2, which shows the proportion of total plastic strain, and proportion of rupture time, spent in each creep regime.

Figure 2: Percentage of (a) strain and (b) time spent in each creep regime for various composites (processed by powder-route or infiltration), and unreinforced powder-route Al tested at 270°C with an initial applied stress of 30 MPa.

Both the primary and secondary regimes are very small, with the tertiary region lasting for the majority of the specimen life in all cases. This suggests that damage is occurring throughout most of the deformation. Conversely, for the unreinforced powder-route material, the majority of the deformation occurs during the secondary creep regime.

Strain to failure data are shown in Fig. 3. Minimum creep rates are shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the composites display significantly differing creep responses. The spherical particulate reinforced composite exhibits the lowest creep resistance, with a high strain to failure and a very short rupture time, whereas the unreinforced powder-route material has a much greater creep resistance. It is interesting to note that the unreinforced powder-route aluminium displays better creep resistance than the short fibre and particulate reinforced composites, although not as good as the whisker reinforced material. The powder-route composites have significantly better creep resistance than the infiltrated material. It is also found that the angular particulate reinforcement gives a better creep resistance than the spherical or any of the short fibre reinforced materials. This is perhaps surprising, since from a load transfer argument, the higher aspect ratio fibres should give the best creep resistance. Similarly, it can be seen that the unreinforced powder-route aluminium material exhibits both lower minimum strain rates and higher rupture times than any of the composites, with the exception of the whisker reinforced material.

Fig. 5 shows minimum creep rates for the Saffil composites produced using the two processing routes, together with unreinforced aluminium, also produced by powder and casting methods. It can be seen that the powder-route composite has much better creep resistance than the infiltrated material. What is also interesting to note is that the unreinforced cast aluminium and the infiltrated Saffil composite show very similar values. This suggests that the load is not being effectively carried by the reinforcement in the infiltrated composite.

Figure 3: Failure Strain for 10 vol% composites tested at 270°C and 300°C with various applied loads fabricated by powder-route (P) or squeeze infiltration (I).

Figure 4: Minimum creep rates for (a) 10 vol% and (b) 20 vol% reinforced composites together with unreinforced powder-route Al tested at 270°C, fabricated by powder-route (P) or infiltration followed by extrusion (I).

DISCUSSION

Effect of Processing Route

Creep Resistance

The initial matrix microstructure was found to be highly dependent on the processing route. The initial grain size was much finer for the powder-route material than for the squeeze infiltrated, and there was a significant extent of fine oxide along the prior particle boundaries of the aluminium. It would therefore be expected that the creep properties of composites prepared using the two methods would be very different. This is confirmed by the creep data. The powder-route composites displayed far better creep resistance than the infiltrated (Figs. 3-5), in terms of failure strain, minimum strain rate and rupture times.

The fine matrix oxide, present in the powder-route composites, has two significant effects. Firstly it results in a fine grain structure by effectively pinning the grain boundaries. Secondly, it provide effective barriers to dislocation motion, thus enhancing the creep resistance of the material.

Figure 5: Minimum strain rates for CP Al 10 vol% Saffil reinforced composites, and unreinforced Al produced by powder-route and squeeze infiltration/casting.

Damage Characteristics

The favoured damage sites were found to be different for the two processing routes. This is demonstrated by Fig. 6 which shows electropolished specimens from the two Saffil reinforced composites taken from regions near the fracture surfaces. In the squeeze infiltrated composites damage occurred at the matrix/reinforcement interface of isolated fibres. This damage was distributed fairly homogeneously throughout the specimen, suggesting that it was stable, and could be accommodated without immediately initiating failure. In the powder-route Saffil composites, the reinforcement distribution was found to be poor, with significant

clustering. Large voids tended to open up in these clustered regions, where there is a high degree of triaxial constraint in the matrix. The cavitation was highly localised near the fracture surface, suggesting that it was unstable, and once formed, rapidly lead to the onset of failure.

It is unfortunate that the reinforcement distributions in these composites were not comparable, thus preventing the evaluation of the effect of matrix oxide on the damage processes. However, the powder-route material still displayed significantly better creep resistance than the infiltrated. This therefore suggests that if the distribution of the fibres during the powder-processing could be improved, this would lead to a composite with significantly better creep resistance.

Figure 6: SEM micrographs showing longitudinal sections of CP Al 10vol% Saffil produced by (a) powder processing, and (b) infiltration, taken from regions near the fracture surface.

Effect of Interfacial Bond Strength

It has been established[7] that the interfacial bond in the Al-Al₂O₃ system is strong. This is consistent with the experimental observation[8,9] that debonding occurs when a critical hydrostatic stress is attained at the interface, rather than a critical normal stress. However, in the case of carbon fibre reinforced Al, the interfacial bond strength is much weaker[10]. It is therefore expected that interfacial sliding and decohesion will occur more readily in the Al-C system than in the Al-Al₂O₃ system. This is consistent with microstructural observations taken from failed specimens of the two composites. For example, Fig. 7 shows regions of failed specimen of Al 10 vol% C fibre, with clear evidence of interfacial failure. It was also found that cavitation occurred extensively throughout the specimens, and was not localised near the fracture surface. This confirms that cavitation at individual reinforcement fibres is very easy in the Al-C system, and that the resulting damage, although lowering the composite stiffness, is stable and does not immediately initiate failure. As has already been observed, the Saffil composites exhibited significant fibre clustering, resulting in large cavities and early failure.

Figure 7: Micrographs of 10 vol% (a) C and (b) SiC_w material, taken near fracture surface

Effect of Reinforcement Shape and Aspect Ratio

Failed specimens of angular and spherical particulate reinforced composites are shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that the spherical reinforcement shows much worse creep resistance than the angular. What is interesting is the surprisingly large difference between the two. Since the initial grain size and structure were very similar, the two matrices are expected to have similar strengths. It is also unlikely that the large difference in creep resistance would be due entirely to the small difference in reinforcement aspect ratio between the two reinforcements (~1.5 compared with 1). Also, from Fig. 4 it can be seen that the angular particulate gave better creep resistance than any of the fibre reinforced composites. If load transfer were dominating the creep response, then the higher aspect ratio reinforcements would be expected to have a better creep resistance than the particulate, which is not observed here.

Figure 8: SEM micrographs showing longitudinal sections CP Al reinforced with (a) spherical and (b) angular alumina, taken from regions near the fracture surface.

Both these effects can be explained if the promotion of damage is taken into account. It has been established[8,9] that high local hydrostatic stresses are evolved adjacent to the reinforcement/matrix interface on loading a composite, and that these stresses promote damage. It has also been shown that the higher the reinforcement aspect ratio, the higher the resulting local stress concentration. Therefore, damage will be expected to occur more readily

in the fibre reinforced materials compared with the particulates. If this is the case, and damage does occur more readily in the fibre reinforced materials, this may accelerate the onset of failure giving these composite inferior creep resistance. This also explains why the unreinforced powder-route Al showed significantly better creep resistance than all composites except the whisker reinforced material (Fig.4). If load transfer were dominating the creep response then the composites would give better performance than the unreinforced material. Clearly this is not the case. This suggests that reinforcement of this size range accelerates the onset of failure by promoting internal damage.

In the case of the particulate reinforcements, the distribution of damage is the key factor. From Fig.8, it can be seen that, for the angular reinforcement, cavities tend to form at individual reinforcement particles and that the distribution is fairly homogeneous. Favoured sites were reinforcement angularities [9]. With the spherical reinforcement, cavities did not tend to nucleate at individual reinforcement particles, but instead large cavities opened up in the matrix. This again agrees with finite element predictions [9], that the spherical reinforcement shape does not promote cavitation at elevated temperature. The cavities were also highly localised at the fracture surface, showing that damage was unstable. These microstructural observations show that damage can be accommodated more easily in the angular reinforced material, without leading to failure of the composite. This therefore explains why the angular material showed much better creep resistance than the spherical material.

Effect of Reinforcement Scale

Creep data have shown (Fig. 4) that the whisker reinforcement gave enhanced creep resistance (relative to unreinforced powder-route Al), whereas short fibres were detrimental to the creep resistance. Both reinforcements had an average aspect ratio of 5, so purely on load transfer arguments, their behaviour would be expected to be similar. Clearly this is not the case here.

Experimental observations suggest that the difference in creep properties between the two composites is due to the size of the cavities. It has been shown [4] that when a cavity is nucleated at a reinforcement the size of the cavity is directly related to the size of the reinforcement. Also, since both composites had the same volume fraction of reinforcement (10 vol%), the actual number of whiskers, and hence potential cavitation sites, was much larger than for the short fibre system. For this reason, in the whisker reinforced material, the damage tends to form as a large number of very small cavities (Fig. 7). This observation has also been confirmed by neutron diffraction studies [5]. This contrasts with the short fibre material, where fewer large cavities were observed. Since it is more likely that large cavities will coalesce, this explains why damage was found to limit the creep life of the short fibre reinforced material. In the case of the whisker material, a high level of damage could be accommodated without leading to failure. Therefore, the beneficial effects of load transfer to the reinforcement dominated the composite behaviour. These observations demonstrate that the scale of the reinforcement is important in determining the creep behaviour.

Damage Sites and Distribution

The formation of damage within a composite is not necessarily detrimental to the subsequent creep resistance (or at least, the resistance to creep rupture). The important factor is whether or not that damage is stable. Stable cavitation can act to relax local stress concentrations, and

hence delay the onset of failure. Previous work [4,11] on tensile deformation in these materials has shown that significant damage can be accommodated without accelerating the onset of failure. Whether stable cavities can form in the composite essentially depends on the distribution of that damage in the composite, and the ease with which the cavities can grow and coalesce. Cavitation is favoured by reinforcement angularities and elongation parallel to the applied stress. The shape of the angular particulates and short fibres therefore promoted cavitation at the reinforcement/matrix interface, while that of the spherical particulates did not. This is demonstrated by Figs. 6-8 which show typical regions of failed composite. This agrees with the experimentally favoured cavitation sites observed during tensile deformation at elevated temperature [8]. The distribution of the reinforcement is critical in determining the sites and extent of damage in the composites. Where the reinforcement distribution was homogeneous, then reinforcement shape was the dominant parameter controlling cavitation. However, if there were a significant extent of clustering in the reinforcement, then the resulting high triaxial constraint led to preferential formation of large cavities, rather than small cavities at individual reinforcement fibres or particles. Microstructural observations showed that where the reinforcement distribution was homogeneous, and the shape of the reinforcement promoted cavitation, cavitation was found to occur throughout the specimen, and was not catastrophic. Such damage can be accommodated within the composite without leading rapidly to failure. However, when damage was localised near the point of fracture, this suggests that the onset of cavitation is catastrophic.

CONCLUSIONS

The scale of the reinforcement is important in determining creep resistance. Larger reinforcements (3 μ m diameter, aspect ratio 5 fibres, 10-13 μ m particulates) reduce the creep resistance relative to unreinforced powder-route aluminium. Fine whisker reinforcement (1 μ m diameter, aspect ratio 5) enhances the creep resistance relative to unreinforced powder-route aluminium. Composites produced by powder-processing show significantly better creep resistance than those produced by squeeze infiltration. This is due to the fine oxide dispersion in the powder matrices, which inhibits both dislocations motion and recrystallisation. For the larger reinforcements, the site and distribution of damage is more important than load transfer considerations for determining creep resistance.

Reinforcement distribution is critical in determining damage distribution. Clustered regions of reinforcement are favoured sites for severe cavitation. If damage occurs at isolated reinforcement particles or fibres, it is favoured by reinforcement elongation parallel to the applied stress and by reinforcement angularities. When cavitation occurs at isolated reinforcement particles or fibres, it can be tolerated without immediately leading to failure. Such cavitation can be beneficial in relaxing local stress concentrations. When damage is associated with reinforcement clusters, or occurred within the matrix, the cavities are highly unstable, and rapidly lead to failure of the composite.

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